

15.4 kg P/ha were applied uniformly. The crop was raised following the KAU package of recommended practices.

Protein contents of leaf, sheath, culm, and panicle were analyzed by the improved Kjeldahl method ($N \times 6.25$).

Protein yield was worked out by multiplying protein content of a sample by sample dry weight, expressed in kg/ha. Protein content in source and sink was also worked out as percentage of total protein produced (Table 1, 2).

Protein content in leaf, sheath, and culm decreased with increased K up to

29.1 kg K/ha (Table 1). Protein yield increased with K level, a 106% increase in plants treated with 58 kg K/ha.

Plants treated with 58 kg K/ha contained 71.6% of the total protein in the sink.

In general, protein content of source (leaf, sheath, or culm) decreased with kinetin spray, with a corresponding increase in grain protein content. Two sprays of kinetin resulted in accumulation of the highest amount of protein in the grain (9.37%). Protein yield also increased with kinetin spray.

The sink of plants treated with two sprays of kinetin contained 507 kg protein/ha, 71% of total protein.

There was a significant negative correlation between grain yield and protein content of leaf (-0.72**), sheath (-0.81**), and culm (-0.39**); there was a significant positive correlation between grain yield and protein content of panicle (0.91**).

The K-kinetin interaction was significant on protein content of leaf, sheath, and panicle, and synergistic on grain protein and total protein yield (Table 2). Application of 29.1 kg K/ha with two sprays of kinetin resulted in the highest accumulation of protein in the sink (73.6%). These results indicate a synergistic $K \times$ kinetin interaction to mobilize protein from source to sink. □

Table 1. Influence of K and kinetin on protein content and protein yield of different plant parts. Trivandrum, India, 1987 summer.

Treatment	Protein content at harvest (%)				Protein yield at harvest (kg/ha)		Percentage of total protein in	
	Leaf	Sheath	Culm	Panicle	Panicle	Total	Source	Sink
No K	3.62	3.73	4.06	6.65	250.6	418.9	40.2	59.8
14.5 kg K/ha	3.47	3.60	4.01	8.40	405.5	596.0	32.0	68.0
29.1 kg K/ha	3.22	3.53	3.95	8.96	469.7	667.5	29.6	70.4
58.1 kg K/ha	3.23	3.54	3.91	9.55	517.8	723.0	28.4	71.6
Water spray	3.49	3.64	3.97	7.52	318.1	489.2	35.0	65.0
10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.41	3.61	4.02	8.02	372.1	554.3	32.9	67.1
10 ppm kinetin at 10 d after flowering (DF)	3.33	3.59	3.99	8.65	445.9	647.8	31.2	68.8
10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	3.32	3.54	3.95	9.37	507.4	714.2	29.0	71.0
LSD (0.05)	0.11	0.04	ns	0.24	27.9	39.2	-	-

Table 2. Potassium \times kinetin interaction on protein content and protein yield of different plant parts. Trivandrum, India, 1987 summer.

Treatment combination	Protein content at harvest (%)				Protein yield at harvest (kg/ha)		Percentage of total protein in	
	Leaf	Sheath	Culm	Panicle	Panicle	Total	Source	Sink
No K + water spray	3.69	3.78	4.08	5.73	166.9	307.4	45.7	54.3
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.55	3.78	4.07	6.07	186.3	330.7	43.7	56.3
+ 10 ppm kinetin at 10 d after flowering (DF)	3.56	3.75	4.04	6.54	262.6	451.1	41.8	56.2
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	3.66	3.59	4.05	8.26	386.5	586.3	34.1	65.9
14.5 kg K/ha + water spray	3.56	3.63	4.08	7.14	290.1	473.4	38.7	61.3
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.59	3.68	4.04	8.13	360.1	540.5	33.4	66.6
+ 10 ppm kinetin at 10 DF	3.43	3.57	4.01	8.56	419.8	612.2	31.4	68.6
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	3.31	3.53	3.92	9.76	552.1	757.9	27.1	72.9
29.1 kg K/ha + water spray	3.44	3.61	4.04	7.89	358.3	538.6	33.5	66.5
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.34	3.49	4.03	8.12	390.1	581.0	32.9	67.1
+ 10 ppm kinetin at 10 DF	3.15	3.55	3.93	9.80	544.8	754.9	27.8	72.2
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	2.96	3.45	3.80	10.02	585.4	795.6	26.4	73.6
58.1 kg K/ha + water spray	3.26	3.55	3.69	9.33	456.8	637.5	28.3	71.7
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.16	3.48	3.95	9.76	552.1	764.8	27.8	72.2
+ 10 ppm kinetin at 10 DF	3.16	3.52	3.98	9.68	556.5	772.9	28.0	72.0
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	3.35	3.61	4.01	9.44	505.7	716.9	29.5	70.5
LSD (0.05)	0.21	0.08	ns	0.48	55.7	78.4		

Effect of plant growth regulators on ripening, grain development, and rice quality

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We studied the effect of plant growth regulators in a pot experiment laid out in a completely randomized block design with four replications.

IR6 seedlings were transplanted at 30 d after seeding, 3 seedlings/240-mm-diameter, 300-mm-deep pot. An aqueous solution of 100 ppm gibberellic acid (GA_3) and 100 ppm indoleacetic acid (IAA) were sprayed at 3 ml/plant at panicle initiation.

Application of growth regulators at panicle initiation significantly affected plant height, tillers/plant, grains/panicle, 1,000-grain weight, sterility, abortive kernels, grain yield, and protein content (see table). Higher, better quality yield with GA_3 and IAA may be the result of more efficient, vigorous leaves and other plant parts for a longer period because of delayed senescence in treated plants. □

Effect of plant growth regulators on yield components and rice quality. Dera Ismail Khan, NWFP, Pakistan, 1986 summer.

Treatment ^a	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./plant)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)	Sterility (%)	Abortive kernels (%)	Grain yield (g/pot)	Protein content (%)
Control	81 c	12 b	103 c	21 b	10 c	3 b	23 c	7 b
Gibberellic acid (GA ₃) 100 ppm at panicle emergence	92 a	16 a	114 b	22 a	8 b	2 a	38 b	8 a
Indoleacetic acid (IAA) 100 ppm at panicle emergence	89 b	16 a	117 a	22 a	7 a	3 b	40 a	8 a

^aIn a column, numbers followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% level of probability by DMRT.

Crop management

Nursery management for rice grown in intermediate deep water

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Experiments on seedbed management were conducted in a farmer's field during 1985 and 1986 wet seasons. Soil was an alluvial, sandy loam type with pH 6.0, CEC 12 meq/ 100 g soil, 0.74% organic C, and 4 ppm available P.

Seedlings of Tilakkachari (an improved selection) and CR1018 (high-yielding variety) were grown by sowing seeds at low (200 kg seeds/ha) and high density (400 kg seeds/ha) with three levels of fertilizer (Table 1).

Seedlings were transplanted at 40 and 60 d after seeding. The submergence water level in the main field varied from 15 to 60 cm during most of crop growth.

Rice plants grown from seedlings raised in the low seed density nursery performed better (productive tillers, grains/panicle, and yield) than plants grown from seedlings raised in the high density nursery (Table 1). Plants grown from seedlings that received N₃₀P₁₅ in the nursery bed also produced significantly higher yield than treatment N₃₀P₀ or no NP.

Applying N₃₀P₁₅ in the nursery followed by topdressed N₃₀ as urea supergranule further ameliorated

Table 1. Effects of seed rate and fertilizer in nursery on growth and yield of transplanted rice varieties under intermediate submergence (15-60 cm). Kharagpur, India, 1985 and 1986 wet seasons.

Treatment	1985			1986		
	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Variety						
Tilakkachari	213	101	3.7	271	99	4.7
CR1018	323	119	5.2	270	134	4.8
LSD (0.05)	72	2	0.4	ns	6	ns
Seed rate (kg/ha)						
200	284	116	4.5	272	123	4.8
400	252	104	4.3	269	110	4.7
LSD (0.05)	14	3	0.1	ns	2	ns
Fertilizer (kg/ha)						
N ₀ P ₀	235	104	4.0	258	108	4.0
N ₃₀ P ₀	277	108	4.5	268	117	4.9
N ₃₀ P ₁₅	292	118	4.7	288	124	5.3
LSD (0.05)	17	4	0.2	9	2	0.3

Table 2. Effects of seedling age and fertilizer in nursery on growth and yield of transplanted rice varieties under intermediate submergence (15-60 cm). Kharagpur, India, 1985 and 1986 wet seasons.

Treatment	1985			1986		
	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Variety						
Tilakkachari	252	117	3.9	238	106	4.9
CR1018	294	149	5.7	267	133	5.4
LSD (0.05)	ns	15	0.1	ns	11	0.4
Seedling age (d)						
40	256	132	4.4	244	114	5.1
60	290	134	5.2	261	124	5.2
LSD (0.05)	24	ns	0.2	15	6	ns
Fertilizers (kg/ha) in nursery						
N ₀ P ₀	246	120	4.2	223	109	4.6
N ₃₀ P ₀	272	128	4.8	239	118	5.1
N ₃₀ P ₁₅	279	138	5.0	251	124	5.2
Fertilizers (kg/ha) in nursery and in field						
N ₃₀ P ₁₅ and N ₃₀ P ₀ (top-dressing)	295	146	5.3	298	127	5.8
LSD (0.05)	10	4	0.2	8	3	0.2